

A Paradigm Shift in Learning Process – A Case Study

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Abstract - Learning is one of the prime traits that differentiates human beings from other creatures. Human beings explored this faculty profoundly. Indians are one among the few in the world whose learning abilities are quite good. They are not only popular for their learning abilities but are also quite good students in their approach and attitude towards teachers. They have always respected teachers and gained knowledge and information from teachers in the face to face interaction / contact learning. Majority of the student community always preferred face to face interaction with teachers and not distance mode / online learning, in spite of the increasing opportunities to learn online / distance mode. Suddenly, Covid-19, a pandemic created challenging times to both students and teachers. Hence, majority of the student community that liked to learn by attending school / college has no other option than to explore and learn online. At the same time, teachers also started exploring various technological tools to reach out to students and fulfil their obligation to quench the thirst of the students to learn. This paper presents the data of the opinions of the students of first year of Engineering to that of third year of engineering with regard to exposure to online learning / tools, ideas, likes and dislikes of learning modes based on the survey conducted with the help of google forms.

Key Words: Online Learning, Students, Teachers and Covid-19.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning plays a major role in the lives of human beings both in terms of quality and economic well-being. Whereas to learn, one needs to have an academic ambience, knowledgeable teachers to teach, libraries with good book bank, and enthusiastic learners around to name a few. All these facilities are normally expected to be available in schools / colleges. But in challenging times such as Covid-19, it is very difficult to reach out to schools / colleges and learn with all these facilities. Yet, students are expected to cope with pandemic situation and learn without wasting much of their time. Under these challenging times, technological era is paving way to learn with online tools. Whereas, in the minds of the majority of the Indian parents, it is believed that students should regularly visit school / college and learn from the face to face interaction of the teachers.

In the Indian context, very rarely, schools / colleges adopt the online teaching as part of their curriculum. Only a few universities that too in western countries adopted online teaching to teach a part of their total teaching program for

the various courses offered by them. This presents the scenario and impression of parents, teachers and students that one can learn and earn degrees only with the help of regular teaching in schools / colleges and not in any other form such as online learning. In spite of the fact that distance mode of learning is fast catching up with working professionals who want to enhance their career and also to fulfil their desire to upgrade their qualifications on personal front.

On the other hand, technological teaching platforms such as Coursera, Edx, Udemy Inc., Khan Academy, Bijus, etc., are serving the student community in a big way across the globe. Yet, majority of the organizations, parents and students treat these teaching platforms as supplementary but not the front-end tools to learn. May be this is the reason why the degree / diploma certificate earned by attending the school / college is considered as qualification for the job by professional organizations across the world even today.

Challenging times always forces people to come up with various alternatives and Covid-19 pandemic situation is no exception. Parents, teachers and students turned towards exploring online teaching and learning tools. Thus, online teaching / learning is playing a major role at the present time and will continue to play in the days to come in the teaching-learning process looking at the present situation. This paradigm shift in teaching-learning process triggered the interest of the faculty to find out what is the opinion, exposure, likes and dislikes of the students with regard to face-to-face interaction / regular classwork and online learning with the help of google forms.

2. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this paper are to find out the exposure of students to online learning, their opinion on online learning before the pandemic situation and their take on blended learning, the hurdles that they face in online learning, the support that they need in online learning and finally what makes them to feel complete in the learning process.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted to meet the above objectives is to enquire and find out the details from students with the help of online questionnaire with multiple choice questions in the google form along with an option to pen their ideas, if any.

4. SUBJECTS

The students chosen to study for this small-scale research are from III-year Computer Science Engineering and students from I year Electronics and Communication Engineering. Students are chosen randomly from Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology, an engineering college of repute in the State of Telangana, India.

5. ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRE

Online Questionnaire link is shared with the students to submit their views on questions such as contact learning and online learning before lockdown, and on online learning owing to pandemic Covid-19 with multiple choice options along with an option to write if they want to share anything other than those options. The questions with the options chosen are as follows:

5.1 Presentation of data on Contact Learning before lockdown in the following figures of 1.1 and 1.2.

Fig. 1.1 Response of the I-year students of engineering

Fig. 1.2 Response of the III-year students of engineering

- Around 36.7% of students of I year and 53.8% of students of III year feel that contact learning should be supported with online learning before the lockdown.
- Around 40% of students of I year and 33.3% of students of III year feel that contact learning and homework is fine before the lockdown.
- Around 10% of students of I year and III-year state that they have not heard of online learning before the lockdown.
- Around 13.3% of students of I year feel that contact learning is the only option and 2.6% of students of III year feel that contact learning is good as it is interactive and engaging.

5.2 Presentation of data on Online Learning before the down in figures 2.1 and 2.2.

Fig. 2.1 Responses of I year students of engineering

Fig. 2.2 Response of the III-year students of engineering

- Around 46.7% of students of I year and 17.9% of students of III-year state that they have not tried online learning before pandemic covid-19.
- Around 20% of students of I year and 30.8% of students of III year have no exposure to online learning before pandemic covid-19.
- Around 16.7% of students of I year and 10.3% of students of III year have no idea about online learning before pandemic covid-19.
- Around 12.8% of student of III year of engineering state that they have no equipment for online learning.
- Some minor chunks of students of I year and III-year state that online learning is good. They have learnt certain concepts beyond syllabus. Whereas, some students have issues such as internet facility, audio/video, no proper equipment, and feel some interaction with teachers is a big shortfall in it.

5.3 Adoption of online learning after two terms of lockdown given in the following figures of 3.1 and 3.2.

Fig. 3.1 Response of the I year students of engineering

Fig. 3.3 Response of the III-year students of engineering

- Around 36.7% of I year students and 38.5% of III-year students have come to consensus that online learning is fine after two terms of lockdown during Covid-19 pandemic situation.
- Around 23.3% of I year students and 20.5% of III-year students opine that online learning should be supplemented with contact learning after two terms of lockdown during Covid-19 pandemic situation.
- Around 16.7% of I year students and 15.4% of III-year students feel that online learning with homework such as reading, and writing is fine after two terms of lockdown during Covid-19 pandemic situation.
- Around 7.7% of III-year students feel that online learning is the best option after two terms of lockdown during Covid-19 pandemic situation. And a minor chunk of students has varied options such as issues with internet facility, audio/video issues, time restrictions, so on and so forth.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the data collected from the students of III and I year it is clear that before the Covid-19 pandemic situation around 75% and more number of students feel that face to face interaction / contact learning is the most preferred option and if required it may be supplemented with homework such as reading / writing or online learning / teaching. Around 10% and more number of students of both III and I year have not heard of online learning before lockdown. Around 70% to 80% of III year and I year students have not tried online learning or have no exposure or do not have equipment for online learning before Covid-19 pandemic situation. This clearly shows how students preferred and completely dependent on face to face interaction with teachers for learning. A paradigm shift in the learning option took place in the minds of the students of both III year and I year after the two terms of lockdown owing to Covid-19 pandemic situation. Around 7.7% of III-year students very clearly said Online learning is the best. Around 75% students very clearly given their mandate that online learning is fine, and it may be supplemented with homework such as reading / writing or if required interaction with teacher online/offline. Of these 75%, blended learning is opted by around 20-25% of students both in III- and I-year students. The paradigm shift in

thinking is very clearly evident after the Covid-19 pandemic situation. It is expected that this shift will continue to impact teachers, parents and students to stick to online learning in the days to come even after Covid-19 situation.

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BIOGRAPHIES

Venkata Ramana Kolluru with 13 years of teaching experience in English to undergraduate engineering students and also taught subjects such as Professional Ethics, Constitution of India, Gender Sensitization Lab.